

JISMONIY MADANIYAT VA SPORT SOHASIDA OLIY O'QUV YURTIGA KIRISH BO'YICHA TAYYORGARLIKNING DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI.

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada jismoniy madaniyat va sport sohasida oliy o'quv yurtiga kirish bo'yicha tayyorgarlikning dolzarb muammolari haqida fikr yuritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Jismoniy madaniyat, jismoniy va ma'naviy yetuk, kadrlarning yuqori qo'nimsizligi.

URGENT PROBLEMS OF TRAINING FOR ADMISSION TO A HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION IN THE FIELD OF PHYSICAL CULTURE AND SPORTS.

Abstract. This article reflects on the pressing problems of training for admission to a higher educational institution in the field of Physical Culture and sports.

Key words: Physical Culture, physical and spiritual mature, high non-landing of personnel.

АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ ПОДГОТОВКИ К ПОСТУПЛЕНИЮ В ВЫСШЕЕ УЧЕБНОЕ ЗАВЕДЕНИЕ В ОБЛАСТИ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ И СПОРТА.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассмотрены актуальные проблемы подготовки к поступлению в высшее учебное заведение в области физической культуры и спорта.

Ключевые слова: физическая культура, физическая и духовная зрелость, высокая текучесть кадров.

Prezidentimiz tomonidan yoshlarga berilayotgan e'tibor juda ahamiyatlidir. "Hozirgi vaqtda mamlakatimiz aholisining 32 foizini yoki 10 millionini 30 yoshgacha bo'lgan yoshlarimiz tashkil etadi. Yoshlarimiz haqli ravishda Vatanimizning kelajagi uchun javobgarlikni zimmasiga olishga qodir bo'lgan, bugungi va ertangi kunimizning hal etuvchi kuchiga aylanib borayotgani barchamizga g'urur va iftixor bag'ishlaydi.

Bu sohada olib borayotgan keng miqyosli ishlarimizni, xususan, ta'lim-tarbiya bo'yicha qabul qilingan umummilliy dasturlarimizni mantiqiy yakuniga yetkazishimiz zarur.

Shu maqsadda hukumatning, tegishli vazirlik va idoralar hamda butun ta'lim tizimining, hurmatli domlalarimiz va professor-o'qituvchilarning eng muhim vazifasi - yosh avlodga puxta ta'lim berish, ularni jismoniy va ma'naviy yetuk insonlar etib tarbiyalashdan iboratdir.

Farzandlarimiz uchun zamonaviy ish joylari yaratish, ularning hayotda munosib o'rin egallashini ta'minlashga qaratilgan ishlarimizni yangi bosqichga ko'tarishni davrning o'zi taqozo etmoqda", deb alohida ta'kidlaganlar va oliy o'quv yurtlariga qamrovni 60 % ga chiqarish vazifasi qo'yilgan[2].

Yosh avlod – tarbiya tizimining tarkibiy qismi asosida jismoniy tarbiya ta'limi yotadi. Ta'lim jarayonining bu jabhasi o'quvchilarni har tomonlama jismoniy, ruhiy va ma'naviy fazilatlarini tarbiyalash, hayotga, mehnatga, Vatan mudofasiga tayyorlash, jismoniy kamolotga erishish uchun zarur jismoniy zaxiralar bankini o'zida mujassamlashtirgan jamiyat a'zosini shakllantirishdek, maqsad uchun xizmat qiladi.

Jismoniy madaniyat va sport sohasida mutaxassislarni tayyorlashda yangi yo'nalishlarni izlash oliy o'quv yurtida ilmiy-pedagogik jarayonni yaxshilashning asosiy yo'llaridan biri hisoblanadi.

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining "O'zbekiston Respublikasida jismoniy tarbiya va sportni yanada takomillashtirish va ommalashtirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi Farmonida ham "... 2025-yilgacha davlat sport ta'limi muassasalarida trener va mutaxassislarning sifat tarkibi, xususan, oliy ma'lumotli xodimlar sonini bosqichma-bosqich 80 foizgacha yetkazish..." asosiy yo'nalishlar qilib belgilangan[2].

Bu o'z navbatida yoshlarni oliy o'quv yurtigacha tayyorlash sohasiga ham jiddiy e'tibor qaratishni taqozo etadi. Ayniqsa, jismoniy tarbiya va sportni yanada ommalashtirish va bu sohada zamon talablariga mos keluvchi malakali kadrlarni tayyorlash ham dolzarb masalalardan biridir.

Biz tadqiqotlarimizni umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablari bitiruvchi sinf o'quvchilari bilan olib bordik va ularni jismoniy tarbiya va sport sohasida oliy ta'lim muassasalariga tayyorgarlik darajasini o'rgandik.

Kadrlarning yuqori qo'nimsizligi va motivatsiyaning pastligi jismoniy madaniyat va sport sohasidagi oliy o'quv yurtlariga kirish uchun o'quvchilar kontingentini saqlash va saralab olishni takomillashtirish yo'llarini qidirib topish masalasini ilgari suradi.

Maktab o'quvchilari va talabalarni jismoniy madaniyat mashg'ulotlariga va pedagogik faoliyatga motivatsiyasi o'rganildi. Natijalar tahlili ko'rsatdiki, ya'ni jismoniy sifatlarni rivojlantirish bilan bog'liq (84.3%), maktab o'quvchilarini jismoniy madaniyat bilan shug'ullanishga xohishi va tanlangan sport turidan yuqori natijalarga erishish (68.7%) ko'proq ta'sirli motivlar hisoblanadi. Talabalarda esa bu motivlar mos ravishda 53.2% va 31% ni tashkil qildi. Salomatlikni mustahkamlashni 21 % maktab o'quvchilari va 38.4 % talabalar belgiladilar.

Pedagogik faoliyatni tushunib yetishda motivatsiya asosiy hisoblanadi. Pedagogik faoliyatga qiziqish tarbiya va o'qitish bilan bog'liq, kasbiy faoliyatga shaxsni intilishi sifatida tushuniladi. Natijalarni tahlili ko'rsatdiki, bu bir qancha maktab o'quvchilarida noto'g'ri tushuncha bilan yondoshishidan darak beradi, bu esa ularni jismoniy madaniyat va sport sohasidagi kasbiy faoliyat to'g'risida kerakli axborotga ega emasligi va unda o'z kuchini sinash uchun imkoniyat berilmaganligini bildiradi. Shuning uchun maktab o'quvchilariga kasbni tanlash va pedagogik faoliyat to'g'risida qo'shimcha mashg'ulotlar o'tkazilishi zaruriyati mavjud.

Maktab o'quvchilarida yuqori darajada kasbiy qiziqishni shakllantirish tanlangan kasbga ishtiyoqni yuqori va past-o'rta darajada ifodalanishiga asoslanadi. Maktab o'quvchilarida kasbga yuqori darajada qiziqish hali shakllanmagan bo'ladi. Pedagogik faoliyatga qiziqishni namoyon bo'lishini solishtirma tahlili talabalarda yuqori darajada ko'rinishi so'ralganlarning 58.3 %, shakllangan kasbiy qiziqish esa 38.5% ekanligini ko'rsatdi.

Hozirgi kunda Prezidentimiz tomonidan jismoniy tarbiya va ommaviy sportni yanada rivojlantirishga katta e'tibor qaratilmoqda va bu soha bo'yicha tegishli vazifalar belgilab berilgan.

Shuning uchun jismoniy tarbiya va sport sohasida oliy malakali mutaxassislarni tayyorlash masalasiga jiddiy e'tibor qaratilib, oxirgi yillarda xorijiy davlatlarning oliy ta'lim muassasalari bilan hamkorlik borasida juda ko'p shartnomalar imzolandi va oliy ta'lim tizimini yangi bosqichga ko'tarish dolzarb masalaga aylandi.

Mehnatning yuqori shiddatini va unumdorligini ta'minlash uchun dam olish hamda mehnat qilish rejimida metodik jihatdan to'g'ri tashkil qilingan jismoniy tarbiya va sport

mashg'ulotlarining ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi isbotlangan. Bunday mashg'ulotlar funktsional imkoniyatlar darajasini, jismoniy va emotsional barqarorlikni oshiradi, kasallanishni kamaytiradi, ishga kirishib ketish jarayonining tezlashishini, ishchi harakatlarning optimal sur'ati, tezligi hamda tejamligini uzoq vaqt saqlay olish qobiliyatini ta'minlaydi (L.P.Matveev, 2005).

O'quvchi yoshlar jismoniy tarbiyasini samarali boshqarish uchun shug'ullanuvchilarning jismoniy holati va jismoniy mashqlar bilan shug'ullanish jarayonida qo'llanilayotgan vosita va metodlar ta'sirida organizmdagi o'zgarishlar to'g'risidagi ob'ektiv informatsiya talab qilinadi.

Tadqiqotlar ko'rsatdiki, talabalar jismoniy tarbiyasida sog'lomlashtirish va pedagogik vazifalar bir-biri bilan uzviy bog'liq. Jismoniy tarbiyani ratsional amalga oshirilishi o'quv yili davomida talabalarni tezkor nazorat qilish yo'li bilan har bir kursda jismoniy rivojlanishi va harakat tayyorgarligi xususiyat-larini hisobga olgan holda amalga oshiriladi. Nazoratning doimiy tizimi va talabalarning jismoniy tarbiya jarayonini boshqarish, jismoniy mashqlar va sport bilan shug'ullanishga motivatsiyani ta'minlab, ta'lim jarayoni sifatini oshirishga olib keladi.

Ta'limning samarali metodlaridan biri modulli o'qitish hisoblanadi, uning mohiyati shundan iboratki, o'rganuvchilar unga taklif qilingan o'ziga axborotlar bankini kiritgan dastur bo'yicha mustaqil ishlashi mumkin va uning metodik boshqaruvi egiluvchanlikni, shaxsning individual talablariga mos kelishini va uning tayanch (bazaviy) tayyorgarligi darajasini ta'minlashni o'zining maqsadi qilib qo'yadi.

Modulli o'qitishda pedagog koordinator maslahatchi funktsiyasini bajaradi. Amaliyotda modulli o'qitish printsiptan foydalanish o'quv materialin shunday tuzishga olib keladiki, ya'ni bo'limlar bir biridan alohida emas, balki yagona mazmunni o'zgartirmay o'quv materialini tuzish va to'ldirish imkoniyatini beradi.

Yuqoridagilardan ko'rinib turibdiki, talabalar o'rtasida sog'lom turmush tarzini targ'ib qilish, vatanimizning turli sohalari uchun malakali kadrlarni tayyorlash va ularning kasbiy jismoniy tayyorgarligini takomillashtirish zamon talabidir. Lekin oliy o'quv yurtlarining o'quv dasturlaridagi jismoniy tarbiya uchun ajratilgan soat talabalarni kasbiy jismoniy tayyorgarligini rivojlantirish va bo'lg'usi kasbiga har tomonlama tayyorlash uchun yetarli emas.

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